

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF THE CRUSHING PROCESS OF COMPOSITE CRASH BOX

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ABSTRACT

Due to restrictions to bring down fuel consumption and carbon emissions, the recent research and technology innovations are encouraging automakers to apply composite materials in automotive industry because of their benefits over traditional metallic materials including their light weight, high strength, and reduction in manufacturing time. Along with these benefits, composites also have excellent performance related to energy absorption during impact and crash events. Due to pressure for price limitations, the attempts for using composite materials in automotive sector mostly concentrate on the high priced elements per unit mass and the parts having significance in security. Crash box, one of the components of vehicle's frontal bumper system, has those conditions. Traditionally, the development of crashworthiness in composites design relies upon costly experimental testing. The product development cost can be reduced by accurately simulating the progressive failure and energy absorption mechanisms of composite structures. This study proposes a new structure of carbon-epoxy composite crash box; and presents the numerical simulation of the crushing process of a carbon-epoxy composite crash box including both intralaminar (in-plane) and interlaminar (delamination) failure mechanisms in commercial finite element analysis software, ABAQUS/Explicit. The delamination response of the plate is simulated using the cohesive zone method. The simulation results demonstrate very good agreement with the experimental data, showing that the proposed methodology can be used for realistic crush simulations of composite structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

The automotive sector is under constant pressure to bring down fuel consumption and reduce greenhouse gases emissions with an increase in safety requirements. The average emissions from a car are 150 grams of carbon per kilometre. In the European Union (EU), CO₂ emissions restrictions will reduce passenger cars emission limits from 130g of CO₂/km today to a much more difficult to achieve target of 95g of CO₂/km in 2020. The most effective way of bringing down the fuel consumption is to reduce the automobile weight. That is why; the recent research and technology innovations are encouraging automakers to apply new materials in automotive industry for light weight designs.

Fibre reinforced composites are not only light in weight but also stiff, strong and durable. Composite components are some 30 to 50 per cent lighter in contrast to metal components [1]. Moreover, composites provide great potential for absorbing the energy of a crash event and reducing the accompanying accelerations and forces. Energy-absorbing composite components, which are usually designed to dissipate kinetic energy under controlled collapse or disintegration, substantially increase structural crashworthiness in exchange for a reasonable increase in overall vehicle cost. Although there is a demand for increasing the usage of composites, due to price pressure, the studies on applying composite materials in automotive industry concentrate on the highly priced elements per unit mass and the parts having significance in security.

Crash box is the most distinct part that has those conditions. Figure 1 shows the crash box, which is equipped at the front end of its front side frame and expected to collapse with absorbing crash energy prior to the other body parts in case of frontal crash so that the damage of the main cabin frame is minimized and passengers saved their lives.

Figure 1: Frontal bumper system components [2].

Traditionally, the development of crashworthiness in composites design relies upon costly experimental testing. In addition, it is difficult to carry out a meaningful experimental program during the initial design stages and time required for completing the design is quite long. An alternative solution for high development times and cost is the use of advanced computational tools such as Finite Element Analysis (FEA). However, simulating the progressive failure and energy absorption mechanisms of composite structures accurately is very complicated. Composites absorb crash energy through a combination of interlaminar (delamination) and several intralaminar (in-plane) fracture mechanisms such as compressive matrix, tensile matrix, compressive fibre and tensile fibre failures. Mamalis et al. [3] used explicit LS-DYNA to simulate the crash response of square CFRP composite tubes and validated the simulations with experimental results. Hörmann and Wacker [4] also used the LS-DYNA explicit code to simulate thermoplastic crash boxes. El-Hagel et al. studied numerical analysis of the quasi-static axial crush behaviour of aluminium-composite hybrid tube containing filament wound E glass fibre reinforced epoxy over-wrapped around an aluminium tube. A modified Chang–Chang failure model was used for the composite layers with $\pm 45^\circ$ stacking sequence [5]. Indermuehle et al. [6] studied two approaches in ABAQUS to simulate the performance of composite cone structure including the common failure modes of delamination, fracture, and matrix damage. First they implemented a continuum damage mechanics approach using the constitutive model in ABAQUS/Explicit using a VUMAT user subroutine. The second approach is CZONE technology which is an empirically based approach where the behaviour of the composite is modelled through a “crush” material property. As an example for accurate results between test and simulations in ABAQUS, Sokolinsky et al. [7] simulates the crush behaviour of composite sine wave beam made of carbon/epoxy TORAYCA fabric. A continuum shell model was built in this study and the delamination is simulated by using cohesive zone modelling.

In this study, the modelling of crash behaviour in new lightweight composite crash box design is studied using the commercial software ABAQUS. For the intralaminar damage mechanisms, it is required to utilize some failure criteria. Since delamination is one of the predominant forms of failure for the case of crash simulation, in order to reach accurate results, interlaminar damage (delamination) also has to be taken into consideration. That is why, for effective predictive capabilities, cohesive zone modelling (CZM) is adopted for failure analysis for delamination. CZM uses decohesion elements for the modelling of delamination. Decohesion elements use failure criteria that combine aspects of strength-based analysis to predict the onset of the softening process at the interface between laminae, and Fracture Mechanics to predict delamination propagation. Moreover, a novel composite structure has been manufactured and tested and the results of the Finite Element simulation are compared to experimental results.

2 SPECIMEN AND EXPERIMENTAL SET UP

The CRFP specimen discussed here was manufactured as a part of sandwich structure. The main objective of the experimental study is to visualize the behaviour of the composite material under quasi-static compressive loading and to obtain load-displacement curve for verification of the numerical results.

The specimen which is manufactured from Hexcel AS4/8552 carbon-epoxy unidirectional prepregs has $[0/90]_{2S}$ composite lay-up with 1.5 mm wall thickness and is 100 mm long. Manufacturing process is shown schematically in Figure 2a where layers of prepreg are first wound around aluminium mandrel tools and then additional upper and lower skin layers are put on the core layers. The sandwich laminate is vacuum bagged and processed according to the Manufacturer Recommended Cure Cycle (MRCC). The sandwich panel shown in Figure 2b is then cut by a diamond disc cutter into $100\text{ mm} \times 100\text{ mm}$ parts. The compression surfaces is machined to guarantee to be parallel to each other and chamfered in a milling machine. The final weight of the specimen is 56.51 grams. Close-up photo of a finalized specimen is presented in Figure 2c.

Figure 2: (a) Schematic representation of the lay-up method. (b) Manufactured sandwich panel. (c) Finalized crash box specimen.

The specimen is tested in the vertical configuration standing free on the steel surface of the Instron Universal Testing Machine (Model 3369). The upper plate of the experimental rig was moving downwards during the experiments. A self-aligning sphere joint was used to introduce the crushing load from the test frame onto the specimen. Because the corrugated specimen is self-supporting, no supports were used on the specimens. The testing was performed at a quasi-static speed of 0.5 mm/min. Fig. 3 shows the views of the crushed specimen.

Figure 3: Crushed specimen during and at the end of the compression test.

3 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

In this section, a finite element model of the crash box specimen is described in detail. Commercial finite element program ABAQUS/Explicit is used to simulate the progressive failure of the crash box. Both intralaminar (in-plane) and interlaminar (delamination) failure mechanisms are considered in order to simulate the real physics of composites crushing. When compared to the implicit methods, explicit FE methods are more efficient in solving structural problems involving complex contact interactions occurring within a short duration.

Because the geometry of the crash-box and the loading are symmetric with respect to the horizontal and vertical mid-planes, only one quarter of the assembly is analysed and the necessary symmetry conditions are applied on the corresponding interfaces. Figure 4 shows the quarter model. Since two-dimensional shell elements are used in the model, the bead at the point where web and flange meets is also modelled using shell elements as illustrated in Figure 4c.

Figure 4: (a) Quarter model of the composite sandwich structure. (b) Front view with symmetry axes. (c) Illustration of the bead in the assembly.

Simulations of crushing processes can be carried out in quasi-static and impact conditions. In impact conditions, the structure is subjected to decrease in crush speed, from an initial speed to final rest, which is true behaviour of the actual crush. In quasi-static compression, the specimen is crushed at a constant speed. Since energy absorption capability is dependent on the speeds, quasi-static analysis may not be a true simulation of the actual crash condition. However, quasi static simulations are time-effective and easy to control [8]. That is why, in this study, a quasi-static simulation is preferred to perform by using explicit method.

Each of the eight fabric plies were individually meshed with continuum shell elements (SC8R). Continuum shell elements in ABAQUS have the geometry of a three-dimensional solid element but their kinematic and constitutive behaviours are similar to those of conventional shell elements. The velocity of the impactor is chosen as 300 mm/s. This velocity, which is ten times higher than quasi-static test speed, was used to achieve a reasonable run time for the explicit dynamics analysis. Since dynamic effects become significant beyond 500–1000 mm/s, this artificial increase of the velocity does not affect the analysis results [7]. The analysis consists of a single explicit dynamic step. In the simulations, automatic time incrementation is used with element-by-element stable time increment estimates.

3.1 Intralaminar analysis

The undamaged material response is specified by defining an orthotropic linear elastic material. For 2D plane stress conditions, the stress-strain relations for the in-plane components of the stress and strain are of the form as in Eq. (1).

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_1 & -\nu_{12}/E_1 & 0 \\ -\nu_{21}/E_2 & 1/E_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Where E_1 is the Young's modulus in the fibre direction, E_2 is the Young's modulus in the direction perpendicular to the fibres, G_{12} is the shear modulus, ν_{12} and ν_{21} are Poisson's ratios. Table 1 shows the material properties of the AS4/8552 carbon-epoxy composite [9].

Description	Variable	Value
Density [g/cm ³]	ρ	1.58
Longitudinal modulus [GPa]	E_{11}	141
Transverse modulus [GPa]	$E_{22}=E_{33}$	9.75
Principal Poisson's Ratio	ν_{12}	0.267
Shear Moduli in 1-2 plane [GPa]	$G_{12}=G_{13}$	5.2
Shear Moduli in 2-3 plane [GPa]	G_{23}	3.19
Longitudinal Tensile Strength [MPa]	X_{1+}	2200
Longitudinal Compressive Strength [MPa]	X_{1-}	1500
Transverse Tensile Strength [MPa]	Y_{2+}	81
Transverse Compressive Strength [MPa]	Y_{2-}	260
In-plane Shear Strength [MPa]	S	80

Table 1: Material properties of AS4/8552 composite [9].

In ABAQUS, the two dimensional Hashin initiation criteria, is used to predict the onset of damage [10], The equations of Hashin criteria are listed in Table 2 where, σ_{ij} denote the stress components and the tensile and compressive allowable strengths for lamina are denoted by subscripts T and C, respectively. X_T and Y_T denote the allowable tensile strengths in fibre and transverse directions respectively. Similarly, X_C and Y_C denote the allowable compressive strengths in fibre and transverse directions respectively. Further, S_L and S_T denote allowable longitudinal and transverse shear strengths. These strength values are given in Table 1 for AS4/8552.

Tensile fibre failure for $\sigma_{11} \geq 0$	$\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_T}\right)^2 + \alpha \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_L}\right)^2 \geq 1$
Compressive fibre failure for $\sigma_{11} < 0$	$\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_C}\right)^2 \geq 1$
Tensile matrix failure for $\sigma_{22} > 0$	$\left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_L}\right)^2 \geq 1$
Compressive matrix failure for $\sigma_{22} < 0$	$\left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{2S_T}\right)^2 + \left[\left(\frac{Y_C}{2S_T}\right)^2 - 1\right] \frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_C} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_L}\right)^2$

Table 2: Equations for 2D Hashin Damage Initiation Criteria

Damage evolution criteria determines how the material behaves after damage has been initiated. Damage is characterized by the degradation of material stiffness. It plays an important role in the analysis of fibre-reinforced composite materials. Many such materials exhibit elastic-brittle behaviour; that is, damage in these materials is initiated without significant plastic deformation. Consequently, plasticity can be neglected when modelling behaviour of such materials [11]. The response of the material is computed from;

$$\sigma = C_d \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

C_d is the damaged elasticity matrix, which has the form

$$C_d = \frac{1}{D} \begin{bmatrix} (1 - d_f)E_1 & (1 - d_f)(1 - d_m)v_{21}E_1 & 0 \\ (1 - d_f)(1 - d_m)v_{12}E_2 & (1 - d_m)E_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (1 - d_s)G_{12}D \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where

$$D = 1 - (1 - d_f)(1 - d_m)v_{21}v_{12}$$

The d_f variable reflects the current state of fibre damage, d_m reflects the current state of matrix damage, d_s reflects the current state of shear damage. Equations show how the stiffness of the material decreases as the values of the damage variables increase. Once a damage variable for an integration point reaches to a value of 1, that point no longer contributes any strength or stiffness to the model and can be deleted. Matzenmiller et al. [12] point out that the normal stress contributions, induced by Poisson's ratio, are the first to be diminished that they are affected by both damage variables.

3.2 Interlaminar Analysis (Cohesive Zone Modelling)

Delamination is one of the predominant forms of failure and especially for the case of crash of composite structures; the energy is absorbed mainly by delamination process which is likely to occur under mixed-mode loading rather than a single mode. Therefore, a general formulation for decohesion elements dealing with mixed-mode delamination onset and propagation is also required [13]. Decohesion elements use failure criteria that combine aspects of strength-based analysis to predict the onset of the softening process at the interface between laminae, and Fracture Mechanics to predict delamination propagation. Camanho et al. [14], developed zero-thickness volumetric decohesion elements able to capture delamination onset and growth under mixed-mode loading conditions in composite structural components. Cohesive damage zone models relate cohesive surface tractions, σ , to separation, Δ , at an interface where a crack may occur. The law used in this paper is a bilinear relation between the traction and the separation (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Bilinear constitutive equation [16]

Damage initiation is related to the interfacial strength, σ_c , which is the maximum traction on the traction–separation relation as shown in Figure 5 and K is the interface stiffness that relates the resulting tractions at the interface with the opening displacement Δ .

Turon et al [15] demonstrated that interface stiffness, K , should be large enough to provide a reasonable stiffness but small enough to reduce the risk of numerical problems such as spurious oscillations of the tractions and can be estimated using the relation:

$$K_i = \frac{\alpha E_i}{t} \quad (4)$$

Where i denotes the directions of three fracture modes and t is the layer thickness. The effective elastic properties of the composite will not be affected by the cohesive surface if $E_i \ll K_i t$, hence the parameter α is introduced and for values of α greater than 50, the loss of stiffness due to the presence of the interface is less than 2%, which is sufficiently accurate for most problems.

The damage initiation can be calculated by quadratic formula of Eq. (5). In this model, linear softening damage law is used with the mixed-mode fracture energy criteria based on Power law (Eq. (6)).

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_I}{\sigma_{Ic}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{II}}{\sigma_{IIc}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{III}}{\sigma_{IIIc}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (5)$$

$$\left(\frac{G_I}{G_I^c}\right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{II}^c}\right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{G_{III}}{G_{III}^c}\right)^\alpha = 1 \quad (6)$$

G_I^c is normal fracture energy; G_{II}^c and G_{III}^c are shearing fracture energies for Mode-II and Mode-III respectively. G_I is the normal strain energy release rate, G_{II} and G_{III} are shear strain energy release rates for Mode-II and Mode-III respectively. The properties in Eqns. (5) and (6) of the selected material (AS4/8552 carbon-epoxy) are not available in the literature. At that point, after some trials, data for a very similar carbon fibre/epoxy (IM7/8552) is taken from the study of Hallett et al. [16]. The properties used for cohesive zone model is given in Table 3.

σ_{Ic} [MPa]	σ_{IIc} [MPa]	σ_{IIIc} [MPa]	G_I^c [N/mm]	G_{II}^c [N/mm]	G_{III}^c [N/mm]
54	70	70	0.2	0.8	0.8

Table 3: Interlaminar properties of IM7/8552 composite [16]

The viscosity parameter is required to be defined for stability in solving the nonlinear equations. It is difficult to achieve the nonlinear iteration convergence without this parameter. As this slightly affects the CPU time but not the results, values from 10^{-5} to 10^{-3} were recommended. In the model of Chen et al [17] an optimum value of 10^{-4} is chosen. Besides stiffness and viscosity parameters, a friction coefficient, which describes the frictional forces between the surfaces separated, has also to be set in order to calibrate cohesive law. As pointed out in Ref. [7], the friction coefficient between the surfaces of the debonded composite plies was assumed to be 0.3 and the friction coefficient between the composite plate and the rig was taken to be 0.12.

The simulation time is one of the challenges for modelling in ABAQUS. Although continuum shell elements were preferred and element size was increased to reduce the simulation time, mass scaling was also employed to achieve a reasonable run time. The mass of the crash box was increased by two orders of magnitude at the beginning of the analysis using the fixed mass scaling capability of ABAQUS/Explicit. By checking the kinetic and strain energies, it is confirmed that the quasi-static character of the problem was not changed as a result.

In the final model, a uniform mesh with an element size of 1 mm by 1 mm was used for each ply. When simulation time is taken into account, mesh convergence study couldn't have been applied. Element size is indicated as the minimum value that does not cause excessive distortion. As a result, the model, with 56800 elements and 0.01 seconds step time period, required approximately 90 hours of running time on 8-Core computer.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the model that simulates crushing process of the composite crash box with a sandwich structure, the deformation of the specimen is shown in Figure 12. Please note that the model is only a quarter of the structure since the symmetric nature of the structure is taken into account. According to results, it can be said that brittle fracturing crushing mode, the combination of fragmentation and splaying crushing modes, was observed. The load-displacement output of the numerical analysis is given in Figure 7 together with the experimental results. As can be seen from Figure 7, the specimen was crushed by 20 mm. When two curves are compared, it should be noted that by measuring actual interlaminar properties, better accuracy can be obtained. However, when challenges and simulation time are taken into consideration, the accuracies of the peak and average crush load results are accepted as quite reasonable. By calculating the total area under the load-displacement curve, the numerical and experimental results for the absorbed energy were obtained as shown in Figure 8. At the point that the crushed length reached to 20 mm, the numerically obtained value of energy absorbed by the crash box is 435.6 J.

Figure 6: The deformation of the composite crash box with sandwich structure (quarter model).

Figure 7: Comparison of the experimental and numerical load–displacement curves of crash box.

Figure 8: Numerical and experimental results for the absorbed energy for composite crash box.

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, ABAQUS/Explicit finite element code was used to simulate the behaviour of composite crash box with a novel geometry (sandwich structure). AS4/8552 carbon-epoxy material was selected as a model material because of the availability of the material itself as well as the material property database. For the interlaminar properties, data of a similar material, namely T700/8552 were used in model. By determining the crash performance of the sandwich structure experimentally, numerical and experimental results were compared and interlaminar properties were validated. Consequently, the numerical results pertaining to the load-displacement curve as well as energy absorbing capacity of the sandwich structure are close to the experimentally measured values with an acceptable accuracy. As a future work, effect of residual stresses can be taken into account and more accurate results can be obtained.

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